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A perspective on stretchable ionic thermoelectric supercapacitors for wearable applications: Present and challenges ^{EP}

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ABSTRACT

The conversion of sustainable heat sources from the human body into electricity is a promising strategy for self-powered temperature monitoring and power supplies in wearable electronics. Recently, ionic thermoelectrics (i-TEs) have gained considerable attention because of their Seebeck coefficients (mV K^{-1}), which are orders of magnitude larger than those of conventional electronic TEs (e-TEs). In particular, i-TE supercapacitors (ITESCs) based on thermodiffusion under a temperature gradient in redox-free electrolytes exhibit Seebeck coefficients larger than 10 mV K^{-1} . This characteristic solves the requirement for numerous pairs of p/n type TE legs to achieve sufficient output voltage, thereby substantially minimizing device complexity. Therefore, the development of stretchable and wearable ITESCs capable of harvesting human-generated thermal energy is beneficial for future wearable platforms. From this perspective, recent studies have been summarized on stretchable i-TE electrolytes, which hold considerable potential for use in wearable ITESCs and sensors. Furthermore, the challenges of recent ITESCs have been presented, and the perspectives for the development of fully stretchable ITESCs have been provided for future wearable applications.

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I. INTRODUCTION

With the rapid development of an interconnected society of human/devices/data storage, the demand for wearable electronics capable of monitoring physiological signals, body motion, and health-care has substantially increased owing to their beneficial advantages for human life.^{1–4} This advancement in wearable electronics requires miniaturized and lightweight components for low power consumption. Furthermore, the need for sustainable wearable self-powered systems that are sufficiently compact and flexible for integration with traditional electronics is accelerating.^{5–7} Hence, technologies capable of converting energy naturally generated by human body into electricity have attracted attention. One promising strategy for this purpose is the use of triboelectric nanogenerators that harness various types of normal human motion, including finger movements, elbow bending, knee bending, and footstep impacts.⁸

The human epidermis is a beneficial energy resource that can be used to generate electricity by thermoelectric (TE) materials, as it is a continuous thermal source.^{9,10} In electronic TE (e-TE) materials, the hot side possesses a large number of free charge carriers (electrons or holes), resulting in larger entropy than that on the cold side.¹¹

A continuous flow of charge carriers occurs toward the cold side, generating a current under a given temperature gradient (ΔT) (Fig. 1). Furthermore, the ability of e-TE materials for thermal-to-electrical conversion without mechanical moving parts enables flexible integration and miniaturization with preserved efficiency, which is not the case for conventional heat engines whose efficiency drops from 40% to 0.05% when miniaturized.¹² Therefore, e-TE materials are promising candidates for sustainable energy harvesting technologies in wearable applications.^{13,14}

For instance, the integration of e-TE materials on fabrics^{15,16} or flexible substrates^{17–19} powers human-interactive biosensors,^{20,21} electronic skin,²² implantable medical devices,²³ and wearable devices^{24,25} by utilizing human body heat. The capability of e-TE materials, in which the thermodiffusion of electrons/holes occurs under ΔT , has been remarkably improved, but their Seebeck coefficients ($\Delta V_{\text{output}}/\Delta T$, V_{output} is the output voltage) remain low ($\sim 100 \mu\text{V K}^{-1}$). Hence, numerous pairs of p/n type TE legs must be connected to achieve a practically adequate V_{output} .^{26,27} This results in complexity, additional cost, and intricate fabrication procedure for integration, making it unsuitable for wearable heat harvesting applications.

FIG. 1. Schematically illustration for working principles of e-TE and i-TE materials. Classification of i-TE systems associated with two distinct thermogalvanic and thermodiffusion cells.

A. Ionic TE (i-TE)

Another strategy for obtaining enhanced Seebeck coefficients has been demonstrated using two different i-TE working principles (Fig. 1). One principle involves the thermogalvanic cell with redox-active electrolytes, where electrochemical half-reactions continuously occur at hot and cold electrodes under a ΔT .^{28–31} The thermogalvanic cell comprises two electrodes in contact with a redox-active electrolyte containing both the reductant (red) and oxidant (ox) for the corresponding electrochemical half-reaction. The thermogalvanic cell builds an electric potential difference across the two electrodes under ΔT , resulting in Seebeck coefficients of a few mV K^{-1} . As schematically depicted in Fig. 1, when connecting the electrodes with an external resistor, a constant current can be obtained since convection, diffusion, and migration help the shuttle behavior of redox molecules in the electrolyte.

Another i-TE principle relies on the thermodiffusion of ions under a ΔT in redox-free electrolytes. Ludwig and Soret discovered that, when ΔT was applied to electrolytes, the concentration (c) at the cold side was higher than that at the hot side, which is called the Soret effect.^{32,33} At a steady state, the concentration gradient can be obtained as

$$\nabla c = -cS_T \nabla T, \quad (1)$$

where S_T is the Soret coefficient. Eastman proposed the concept that the heat transport (Q^*) is related to the Soret coefficient^{34,35} defined as

$$S_T = Q^*/k_B T^2. \quad (2)$$

The accumulation of cations and anions at the cold side in a closed system can be expressed through heat transport. As the heat transport of each ion typically differs ($Q_+^* \neq Q_-^*$), it leads to thermally induced differences in concentration. Hence, the unbalance in cations and anions concentrations generates V_{output} under ΔT ,

$$V_{\text{output}} = S_i \Delta T, \quad (3)$$

with an ionic Seebeck coefficient (S_i)

$$S_i = \frac{c_+ Q_+^* - c_- Q_-^*}{(c_+ + c_-) T e}. \quad (4)$$

Increased Seebeck coefficients ($>10 \text{ mV K}^{-1}$) originating from thermodiffusion have been reported for various electrolytes.^{36–43}

The principle for the heat-to-electricity conversion of thermodiffusion cells differs from that of thermogalvanic cells and e-TE materials. Two mechanisms generate a constant current flow through the connected circuit if ΔT persists. However, thermodiffusion cells function not as TE generators but as capacitors, because the current gradually diminishes even in the presence of a sustained ΔT .^{44,45} Similar to e-TE materials, when ΔT is set across a redox-free electrolyte, the thermodiffusion of mobile ions from the hot to the cold side induces a concentration gradient (Soret effect), as previously explained.^{46–48} As thermo-diffused ions cannot pass through the electrodes, they accumulate at the interface between electrodes and the redox-free electrolyte, thereby generating V_{output} . If the circuit is connected, the electronic charge from the electrodes compensates for the previously generated V_{output} . This behavior results in an electric double layer at the interface between the redox-free electrolyte and electrode.^{49–52} A sufficient surface area of electrodes enables the conversion of heat energy to electricity with the ionic Seebeck effect, creating an i-TE supercapacitor (ITESC). The stored energy (E) of an ITESC originating from its ionic Seebeck effect during thermal charging can be indicated as

$$E = \frac{1}{2} C V_{\text{output}}^2 = \frac{1}{2} C (S_i \Delta T)^2, \quad (5)$$

where C is the capacitance. Once ΔT vanishes, thermo-diffused ions revert to their initial states. The electronic charges move back in the opposite direction during thermal charging because V_{output} generated by the Soret effect disappears. As the E during thermal charging depends quadratically on the S_i [Eq. (5)], a high S_i is a major parameter for achieving high-performance ITESC.

Wearable and stretchable heat harvesting technologies based on e-TE and thermogalvanic cells have been considerably advanced,^{13,14,53–55} however, the development of stretchable and wearable ITESC is at an

early stage. Herein, this perspective summarizes current studies on stretchable redox-free i-TE electrolytes for ITESCs (Fig. 2 and Table I)^{56–70} and presents the challenge of the current ITESCs for wearable applications. Next, a fully stretchable ITESC⁷¹ featuring a vertical assembly of all stretchable components is addressed for wearable heat harvesting applications. Perspectives for future wearable ITESC, including (1) device structure, (2) i-TE electrolytes, (3) electrodes, and (4) interfaces between electrolytes/electrodes are provided.

II. STRETCHABLE REDOX-FREE i-TE ELECTROLYTES

A. Ternary polymer complex

Spatial mechanical failure and tearing of materials inevitably occur during their use. The self-healing capability with sufficient mechanical stretchability of i-TE electrolytes is a favorable advantage and offers the potential to enhance the lifetime of wearable heat harvesting technologies.^{56–58} Akbar *et al.* designed a stretchable and self-healing ternary polymer complex i-TE electrolyte consisting of polyaniline (PANI), anionic polyelectrolyte [poly(2-acrylamido-2-methyl-1-propanesulfonic acid)] (PAAMPSA), and phytic acid (PA) (Fig. 2).⁵⁶ The ternary PANI/PAAMPSA/PA i-TE electrolyte exhibited self-healing capabilities without the help of external driving force owing to the dynamic interactions among the three constituents. The stretchability was dependent on relative humidity (RH) and the maximum stretchability was 750% at 80% RH. The i-TE electrolyte displayed the capability of autonomously restoring its initial shape without external driving force for consecutive 30 cutting/healing cycles. Furthermore, the i-TE electrolyte provided pathways for the transport of dissociated mobile protons from multivalent PA. When subjected to a ΔT , the protons can be diffused by protonated sulfonic acid ($-\text{SO}_3\text{H}$) in PAAMPSA. As a result, the i-TE electrolyte showed a positive S_i of 1.3 mV K^{-1} at 50% RH and 8.1 mV K^{-1} at 90% RH, respectively. The ionic conductivity (σ_i) and thermal conductivity (k) of the i-TE electrolyte were 237 mS cm^{-1} and $0.451 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$, respectively, at 90% RH. The V_{output} of 27.9 mV under $\Delta T = 4 \text{ K}$ barely changed up to 50% strain (29.2 mV) owing to excellent stretchability. Furthermore, the σ_i , k , and V_{output} of the i-TE electrolyte were retained without noticeable changes after multiple physical cutting and healing cycles.

Thereafter, this group integrated silicon dioxide (SiO_2) nanoparticles (NPs) into ternary i-TE electrolytes and named them organic-inorganic i-TE composites (OITCs).⁵⁷ The incorporation of SiO_2 NPs significantly boosted S_i and σ_i of OITCs owing to the elevated concentration of ionic charge carriers. This effect arises from the fact that the

functional groups in the SiO_2 NPs prompt the dissociation of the protons in the SO_3H and phosphoric acid groups. As a result, the S_i and σ_i at 80% RH increased to 17.9 mV K^{-1} and 187 mS cm^{-1} from 14.9 mV K^{-1} and 122 mS cm^{-1} , respectively. Furthermore, the OITC exhibited S_i of 16.3 mV K^{-1} when subjected to 200% strain, confirming its excellent mechanical stability. Even after undergoing repetitive 25 cycles of physical cutting/healing tests, the OITC reliably maintained the S_i and σ_i . Finally, an ITESC utilizing carbon nanotube electrodes with high surface area achieved an energy density (19.4 mJ m^{-2}) and a power density ($24.3 \mu\text{W m}^{-2}$) under ΔT of 1.8 K.

Recently, the highest ionic figure of merit (ZT_i) of 12.3 at 70% RH and 44.9 at 90% RH has been reported by controlling the thermophoresis of protons in poly(3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene) (PEDOT)/PAAMPSA/PA i-TE electrolytes.⁵⁸ The excellent i-TE performance was primarily due to the control of the concentration of mobile protons, while minimizing the contribution of the counter anions. When the PEDOT/PAAMPSA ratio was increased to 6.2 wt. %, the number of mobile protons was enhanced. However, when the ratio exceeded 9.1 wt. %, the excess PEDOT began to aggregate, thereby negatively contributing to the concentration of mobile protons. Furthermore, the ion diffusion coefficient decreased because of the aggregation of PEDOT. Consequently, PEDOT/PAAMPSA/PA with 6.2 wt. % of PEDOT/PAAMPSA ratio showed optimized S_i of 21.9 mV K^{-1} and σ_i of 309 mS cm^{-1} at 70% RH. The S_i and σ_i of the PEDOT/PAAMPSA/PA i-TE electrolyte maintained 95% and 90% of their original values, respectively, after the multiple self-healing cycles. Similarly, both values maintained more than 95% of their original performance after repetitive 50 stretching/releasing 100% strain cycles.

B. Polymer:ionic liquid (IL)

Numerous studies based on ILs such as electrolytes, sensors, devices, and displays have been extensively conducted because ILs have the advantages of low volatility, thermal stability, and high σ_i .^{72–74} A stretchable i-TE electrolyte consisting of an IL, 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium trifluoromethanesulfonate ($\text{EMIM}^+\text{OTf}^-$), a polymer, poly(vinylidene fluoride-co-hexafluoropropylene) (PVDF-HFP), and a fluoro-surfactant (FS) has been reported.⁵⁹ PVDF-HFP and $\text{EMIM}^+\text{OTf}^-$ were incorporated to provide mechanical stability and a source of thermodiffusion for i-TE performance. Additionally, the $-\text{CH}_2$ and ethylene oxide groups of the FS additives contributed to distinct interactions with the EMIM^+ cations, increasing the thermodiffusion of the EMIM^+ cations. Consequently, a notable

FIG. 2. Schematic overview of stretchable i-TE electrolytes in terms of materials. (1) Ternary polymer complex consisting of PANI (green line), PAAMPSA (yellow line), and PA (red circle), (2) polymer:IL, and (3) ion-conducting hydrogel.

TABLE I. Characteristics of stretchable i-TE redox-free electrolytes recently published in the literature. Stretchability: a tensile strain that can maintain the performance of i-TE electrolytes investigated in the study.

Material	Humidity (%)	Stretchability (%)	S_i (mV K ⁻¹)	σ_i (mS cm ⁻¹)	k (W m ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	ZT_i	Reference
^a PANI/ ^b PAAMPSA/ ^c PA	90	50	8.1	237	0.451	1.04	56
PANI/PAAMPSA/PA/silicon dioxide nanoparticle	80	100	17.9	189	0.477	3.74	57
^d PEDOT/PAAMPSA/PA	70	100	21.9	309	0.358	12.3	58
^e PVDF-HFP/ ^f EMIMOTf/ ^g FS	90	75	38.3	10.7	0.196	2.34	59
PVDF-HFP/ ^h EMIMTFSI/ ⁱ EMIMCl	90	...	30	2.78×10^{-2}	60
PVDF-HFP/EMIMTFSI/ ^j LiBF ₄	90	...	-21	3.06×10^{-2}	61
^k WPU/ ^l EMIMDCA	90	100	34.5	8.4	0.23	1.3	61
^m DMAPS/EMIMDCA	80	...	20.7	56.2	0.095	...	62
ⁿ MACP/EMIMTFSI	-5.4	4.64	0.125
^o PU/EMIMDCA	70	50	25.6	12.8	0.24	0.99	63
WPU/ ^p LiTFSI	40	...	4.41	8.32×10^{-3}	64
WPU/ ^q ChCl/ethylene glycol	90	50	19.5	8.4	0.2	0.46	65
^r PAAm/Sodium carboxymethyl cellulose/ ^s NaCl	...	150	17.1	26.1	66
Gelatin/PAAm/ ^t LiCl/ ^u Li ₂ SO ₄	10.4	~30	67
PAAm/alginate/ ^v PEG/ ^w EMIMBF ₄	19.32	~18	0.53	...	68
PAAm/calcium alginate/Li ₂ SO ₄	...	Compression	11.5	6.24	0.5085	0.048	69
^x P(AM-AANa)/sodium alginate/NaCl	34.27	5.9	0.5522	0.36	70
^y PEGDA/ ^z 2-HEA/EMIMTFSI	90	250	38.9	3.76×10^{-1}	0.215	...	71

^aPANI: polyaniline,^bPAAMPSA: poly(2-acrylamido-2-methyl-1-propane sulfonic acid),^cPA: phytic acid,^dPEDOT: poly(3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene),^ePVDF-HFP: poly(vinylidene fluoride-co-hexafluoropropylene),^fEMIMOTf: 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium trifluoromethanesulfonate),^gFS: fluoro surfactant,^hEMIMTFSI: 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium bis(trifluoromethylsulfonyl)imide,ⁱEMIMCl: 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium chloride,^jLiBF₄: lithium tetrafluoroborate,^kWPU: water-dispersible polyurethane,^lEMIMDCA: 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium dicyanamide,^mDMAPS: [2-(methacryloyloxy)ethyl]dimethyl-(3-sulfopropyl)ammonium hydroxide,ⁿMACP: 2-methacryloyloxyethyl phosphoryl-choline.^oPU: polyurethane,^pLiTFSI: lithium bis(trifluoromethanesulfonyl)imide,^qChCl: choline chloride,^rPAAm: polyacrylamide,^sNaCl: sodium chloride,^tLiCl: lithium chloride,^uLi₂SO₄: lithium sulfate,^vPEG: polyethylene glycol,^wEMIMBF₄: 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium tetrafluoroborate,^xP(AM-AANa): poly(acrylamide-sodium acrylate),^yPEGDA: polyethylene glycol diacrylate,^z2-HEA: 2-hydroxyethyl acrylate.

improvement in the i-TE performance of the electrolyte was achieved. The i-TE electrolyte demonstrated S_i of 38.3 mV K⁻¹, σ_i of 10.7 mS cm⁻¹, and ZT_i of 2.34 at 90% RH. Furthermore, the S_i and σ_i barely changed upon stretching to 75% strain. At 70% RH, S_i was measured as 27.3 mV K⁻¹ at 0% strain and 25.9 mV K⁻¹ at 75% strain. The σ_i decreased slightly to 91.1% of its initial value at 75% strain.

The V_{output} of the i-TE under a given ΔT originates from the difference in the thermodiffusion of mobile ions, which is determined by

the Q^* of the respective ions. The Q^* of ions in the i-TE electrolyte is related to the interactions between ions and the local environment, such as dipole interactions, hydrogen bonding, and Lewis-base interactions.^{27,36,71} Liu *et al.* tuned the sign of S_i in a PVDF-HFP-based i-TE electrolyte by modulating internal ionic interactions.⁶⁰ Without ion doping in the PVDF-HFP/1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium bis(trifluoromethylsulfonyl)imide (EMIM⁺TFSI⁻) i-TE electrolyte, the V_{output} was negligible because the contributions of the EMIM⁺ and TFSI⁻ ions to

thermodiffusion offset each other. However, when lithium tetrafluoroborate (Li^+BF_4^-) was employed in the PVDF-HFP/EMIM⁺TFSI⁻ electrolyte, the Li^+ ions strongly interacted with the TFSI⁻ anions. The Q^* of the BF_4^- anions increased significantly, resulting in a negative S_i of -21 mV K^{-1} at 90 RH%. In contrast, a positive S_i of 30 mV K^{-1} was obtained because the Cl^- ions in 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium chloride (EMIM⁺Cl⁻) established hydrogen bonding with the EMIM⁺ cations in the electrolyte. Ten pairs of p/n types of i-TE electrolytes can generate 0.25 V K^{-1} on the flexible substrate at 60% RH.

Polyurethane (PU), which consists of hard and soft segments, offers significant benefits as a gelator for imparting stretchability to i-TE electrolytes owing to its mechanical properties and structural diversity.⁶¹ Fang *et al.* reported a stretchable i-TE electrolyte prepared by blending water-dispersible PU and 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium dicyanamide (EMIM⁺DCA⁻) IL.⁶¹ The specific ion-dipole interactions between the polar groups of WPU and EMIM⁺DCA⁻ ions rendered a homogenous solution without precipitation and facilitated ionic transportation. The prepared i-TE electrolyte with 40 wt. % EMIM⁺DCA⁻ possessed S_i of 34.5 mV K^{-1} , σ_i of 8.4 mS cm^{-1} , and k of $0.23 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$ at 90% RH. The i-TE electrolyte maintained a reproducible S_i at 50% strain. It slightly decreased from 23.1 to 18.7 mV K^{-1} when stretched to 100% strain. Furthermore, ITESCs with 40% EMIM⁺DCA⁻ in WPU could be thermally charged at 50% strain without noticeable degradation.

Recently, Ho *et al.* reported a different type of i-TE electrolyte based on zwitterionic (ZI) polymers, in which an equal number of positively and negatively charged functional groups were formed within a single chain.⁶² This study modulated the position of the positive and negative moieties of the side chain in ZI polymers. This strategy can effectively control the movement of free ions. For instance, in a p-type ZI electrolyte consisting of [2-(methacryloyloxy)ethyl]dimethyl-(3-sulfopropyl)ammonium hydroxide (DMAPS) and EMIM⁺DCA⁻ ILs, the cation charge carriers (EMIM⁺) interacted with the outer anionic sites in the ion-conducting channels of the ZI polymer, whereas DCA⁻ anions were tightly confined to the inner region. Therefore, thermodiffusion of DCA⁻ anions was restricted when subjected to a ΔT , exhibiting p-type i-TE characteristics. Conversely, in an n-type ZI electrolyte with a combination of 2-methacryloyloxyethyl phosphorylcholine (MACP) and EMIM⁺TFSI⁻, the movement of EMIM⁺ cations was confined. The S_i of the corresponding ZI electrolytes was 20.7 and -5.4 mV K^{-1} at 80% RH. The V_{output} of pairs of 10 i-TE electrolytes was ~ 221 and 1069 mV under a ΔT of 1 and 5 K, respectively. The stretchability of the two ZI polymer electrolytes was dependent on the concentration of the IL additive (EMIM⁺DCA⁻ or EMIM⁺TFSI⁻), and the maximum stretchability was 400% for p-type and 1000% for n-type ZI electrolytes. In this study, a self-healing electrode was prepared by mixing WPU, polyvinyl alcohol (PVA), and liquid metal to develop a self-healing i-TE device. This unique capability empowered users to reconfigure i-TE devices according to the required specifications. For example, assume that a user had two separate i-TE units. The first unit comprised a series of four pairs of ZI i-TE electrolytes with V_{output} of V_1 . The second unit consisted of two pairs and exhibited V_{output} of V_2 . If a user wanted to obtain V_{output} corresponding to $(V_1 + V_2)$, this could be achieved by simply connecting the first and second units through the self-healing capability of the entire device. Thereafter, the resulting device of the six pairs could be divided into two units of three pairs if the customer wanted to decrease the V_{output} to $(V_1 + V_2)/2$.

Although ILs have the advantages of non-volatility, high σ_i , and environmental stability, they present issues such as high cost, toxicity, and leakage.⁷⁵ Zhao *et al.* suggested an alternative i-TE electrolyte consisting of WPU and a deep eutectic solvent (DES) that can form hydrogen bonds with choline chloride (ChCl).⁶⁵ In this study, the state in which the liquid-state DES was present inside the i-TE electrolyte was referred to as eutectogel. This eutectogel had merits, including high σ_i /non-volatility and low cost/biocompatibility. The eutectogel with WPU and ChCl:ethylene glycol exhibited S_i of 19.5 mV K^{-1} , σ_i of 8.4 mS cm^{-1} , and k of $0.2 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$ at 90% RH. The σ_i and S_i of a WPU/DES-50% eutectogel slightly decreased to 7.1 mS cm^{-1} and 18.0 mV K^{-1} at 50% strain, respectively.

C. Ion-conducting hydrogel

Hydrogels are promising candidates for wearable and biomedical applications owing to their outstanding high-water content, biocompatibility, stretchability, and adhesive properties.^{76–78} Yang *et al.* reported a stretchable ion-conducting hydrogel electrolyte consisting of a poly(acrylamide) (PAAm) hydrogel, sodium carboxymethyl cellulose, and sodium chloride (NaCl).⁶⁶ This i-TE electrolyte formed a negatively charged network, prompting the selective thermodiffusion of Na^+ cations and limiting the migration of Cl^- . Consequently, the S_i of the i-TE electrolytes with a 3M NaCl concentration was 17.1 mV K^{-1} . The i-TE electrolyte exhibited a small decrease in σ_i from 26.1 to 22.6 mS cm^{-1} when the strain was increased from 0 to 150%. Similarly, the S_i slightly decreased from 16.8 to 10.4 mV K^{-1} , while it remained $\sim 14 \text{ mV K}^{-1}$ up to 150% strain.

A double network (DN) hydrogel, wherein a rigid and brittle first network and a soft and ductile second network are independently interpenetrated, can effectively dissipate mechanical energy and maintain hydrogel integrity under mechanical deformation. Zhang *et al.* fabricated an ion-conducting DN hydrogel with reversible temperature-dependent adhesive properties, in which physically cross-linked gelatin was the first network and covalently crosslinked PAAm was the second network.⁶⁷ When the hydrogel was attached to the human skin, the body temperature was transferred to the hydrogel. Subsequently, this temperature triggered a change in the gelatin chain, resulting in strong adhesion to the human skin. The DN hydrogel was stretched to 1424% strain. The S_i of the DN hydrogel with lithium chloride (LiCl) and lithium sulfate (Li_2SO_4) ions was 10.4 mV K^{-1} and σ_i was $\sim 30 \text{ mS cm}^{-1}$. Several studies on ion-conducting DN hydrogels for i-TE electrolytes have included PAAm/alginate,⁶⁸ PAAm/calcium alginate,⁶⁹ and poly(acrylate-acrylamide)/sodium alginate.⁷⁰ Although the aforementioned studies exhibited high S_i ($> 10 \text{ mV K}^{-1}$), quantitative changes in the i-TE performance according to various strains have not been addressed. Nevertheless, these studies demonstrated a stable V_{output} in a situation that may induce mechanical deformation and open the potential for a single integrated sensor platform with a self-powered system.

III. CHALLENGES OF CURRENT ITESCS FOR WEARABLE APPLICATIONS

Although stretchable redox-free i-TE electrolytes with giant S_i have been reported for ITESCs, they have limitations in wearable heat harvesting applications. Previous studies on stretchable i-TE electrolytes can be classified in terms of device structure (planar or vertical) and the mechanical characteristic of electrodes (rigid or flexible) (Table II).

TABLE II. Classification of recent ITESCs in terms of device configuration and the mechanical characteristic of the electrode.

Electrode	Configuration	
	Planar structure	Vertical structure
Rigid	[56] [57] [58] [59] [60] [61] [63] [64] [65]	[67] [69] [70]
Flexible	[62]	[66] [68]
Stretchable		[71]

Studies on stretchable i-TE electrolytes with ternary polymer complex and polymer:IL in previous sections^{56–65} have investigated the i-TE performance in a planar-structured device; however, this is not the correct architecture for wearable ITESCs. As the human skin sustainably generates a vertical thermal power of $\sim 20 \text{ mW cm}^{-2}$, the wearable ITESC for the conversion of skin temperature into electricity must be vertically positioned along the z-axis rather than the x–y plane on the human skin (Fig. 3).

Second, ITESCs with ionic hydrogel i-TE electrolytes were characterized in a vertical-structured device with rigid or flexible electrode.^{66–70} Since human motions normally induce a mechanical stretching level of $\sim 50\%$, therefore, the integration of stretchable electrodes should be required for the development of wearable ITESC. Additionally, the evaporation of water inside hydrogels at ambient temperature significantly causes low environmental stability, making it difficult to reliably maintain the i-TE performance for a long time without an additional sealing process.

Hence, ITESCs for wearable applications require (i) the incorporation of mechanically deformable electrodes, (ii) the long-term stability of i-TE electrolytes, and (iii) vertical assembly of the entire structure of the electrodes and i-TE electrolytes. Such fully stretchable ITESCs have not yet been reported because of the absence of stretchable electrodes and stable i-TE electrolytes with stretchability.

IV. A FULLY STRETCHABLE ITESC

To realize a fully stretchable ITESC for wearable ITESC, our group designed a stretchable i-TE electrolyte with environmental stability and stretchability, in which a polyethylene glycol diacrylate

(PEGDA)/2-hydroxyethyl acrylate (2-HEA) polymer matrices were infiltrated with EMIM⁺TFSI⁻ IL.⁷¹ The prepared i-TE electrolyte exhibited environmental stability owing to the minor proportion of nonvolatile constituents. Ion dissociation was enhanced by hydrogen bonding between EMIM⁺TFSI⁻ and the polymer network. Furthermore, the favorable Lewis-base interaction between the EMIM⁺ and PEGDA selectively increased heat transport of the EMIM⁺ cations, exhibiting p-type thermodiffusion under a ΔT . This i-TE electrolyte exhibited S_i of 38.9 mV K^{-1} at 90% RH. Benefiting from the mechanical stretchability of the i-TE electrolytes, the ability to harvest heat when mounted on curved surfaces of different thermal sources, such as monitors, light bulbs, and human skin has been demonstrated. The i-TE performance of the electrolytes retained $\sim 90\%$ of their initial values even when stretched to 250% strain.

Finally, the i-TE electrolyte was vertically positioned between Au-coated titanium dioxide nanowires (Au-TiO₂ NWs) electrodes. Stretchable Au-TiO₂ NWs were transferred onto a thermoplastic polyurethane substrate, and the sheet resistances (R_s) were $3.44 \Omega/\text{sq}$ at 0% to $200.08 \Omega/\text{sq}$ at 300%. Notably, although the R_s of the Au-TiO₂ NWs gradually increased during mechanical deformation, it was still several orders of magnitude lower than that of the i-TE electrolyte. The variation in the R_s of the Au-TiO₂ NWs upon mechanical deformation was negligible compared with that of the i-TE electrolyte. Hence, a fully stretchable ITESC demonstrated charging/discharging behaviors at 60% strain, and its thermal charging was reliable after 500 consecutive 50% strain cycles.

V. PERSPECTIVES FOR WEARABLE ITESCS

This perspective summarizes the recent developments in stretchable i-TE electrolytes and emphasizes the necessity of fully stretchable ITESC for wearable heat harvesting applications. Stretchable i-TE electrolytes have undergone remarkable developments in recent years, with notable advances in high-performance (S_i , σ_i , and ZT_i) and stretchability. A large S_i showed a promising approach for effectively converting low-grade human body temperature into electricity. In addition to the energy harvesting point of view, the high S_i is helpful for wearable temperature sensors in real-time health monitoring. As the sensing range of body temperature is typically in the range of a few degrees (1–2 K), i-TE materials with a high S_i can yield large electric signals and simplify post-processing steps.

FIG. 3. The perspective for future wearable ITESCs for converting vertical thermal power from the human skin. The red arrow indicates the constant thermal power along the z-axis.

For example, Han *et al.* reported ultrasensitive thermal sensor arrays with i-TE hydrogel consisting of cellulose matrix and sodium hydroxide (NaOH).⁷⁹ The i-TE hydrogel arrays were placed on a flexible printed circuit board where five sensing electrodes and a reference electrode were patterned. Once a ΔT was exerted on the thermal sensor arrays, V_{output} was generated since the thermodiffusion of Na^+ ion caused the unbalance between cations and anions. Additionally, humidity-dependent i-TE performance facilitated multiparameter sensor utilizing a planar device structure of PEDOT:cellulose aerogel.⁸⁰ It exhibited the capability to decouple pressure, humidity, and temperature without cross-talks. When increasing humidity higher than 50%, S_i of PEDOT:cellulose aerogel exponentially increased, greatly contributing to total V_{output} .

However, the environment-interactive sensor based on the planar-structured i-TE requires an energy-inefficient interconnected circuit, leading to a bulky device and low density of TE legs. Importantly, it is worth noting that the planar structure is not the right architecture for wearable heat harvesting devices on human skin since thermal power is vertically generated, as previously discussed in section III. Furthermore, i-TE electrolytes with stretchability, high-performance, and environmental stability are necessary to ensure the reliable long-term operation of wearable ITESCs and sensors. In the following section, several future directions with a focus on the device structure, high-performance i-TE electrolytes/electrodes with stretchability, and interfaces between electrode/i-TE electrolyte have been proposed (Fig. 3).

A. Device structure

A fundamental prerequisite for wearable ITESCs is the implementation of an appropriate device structure to harvest heat from the human skin. As discussed previously, human skin sustainably generates a thermal source perpendicular to its surface. A vertically assembled electrode/electrolyte/electrode structure is necessary for thermal-to-electric conversion on the human skin. Due to the lack of integration of stretchable electrodes, previous studies have selected a planar-structured ITESC with rigid electrodes. Furthermore, it has been reported that the hydrovoltaic effect in i-TE electrolytes, wherein the evaporation and absorption of water molecules under a ΔT cause a hydration gradient, can further contribute to V_{output} and stored energy.⁸¹ Hydrovoltaic contribution occurs when the top surface of the i-TE electrolyte is exposed to air without a sealing cover. In vertically assembled ITESCs, both V_{output} and E originate from the true ionic Seebeck effect, because the i-TE electrolyte is sealed with adjacent electrodes to effectively prevent water dynamics. Hence, the vertical-structured ITESCs are essential to convert heat generated by human skin into electricity and accurately distinguish the true energy contribution between the hydrovoltaic and Soret effects. Otherwise, when measuring the i-TE performance of a planar-structured ITESC, the top surface of electrolytes must be covered to decouple the two contributions under a ΔT .

B. Stable electrolytes with enhanced i-TE performance

To develop wearable ITESC, the challenge of a relatively low σ_i compared with liquid i-TE electrolytes and conventional e-TE materials should be overcome. Strategies previously employed for liquid i-TE electrolytes can enhance the performance of stretchable i-TE electrolytes (S_i , σ_i , and ZT_i). Various strategies have recently been reported to increase ion mobility and create selective ion diffusion channels in

host polymer matrices or liquid electrolytes. For example, metal-organic frameworks,⁸² inorganic NPs,⁸³ and negatively charged cellulosic membranes⁸⁴ have been demonstrated to improve S_i and σ_i . Qian and coworkers introduced zeolitic imidazolate framework (ZIF-8) to EMIM⁺DCA⁻ IL, significantly enhancing S_i from 8.8 to 31.9 mV K⁻¹.⁸² The increase in the S_i is primarily due to the selective boost for EMIM⁺ ion mobility by ZIF-8. Furthermore, when inorganic SiO₂ NP was added into EMIM⁺DCA⁻ IL, the favorable interaction between hydroxy groups on the surface of SiO₂ NPs and DCA⁻ ions established an ionic transport pathway.⁸³ The interaction prompted the dissociation of EMIM⁺ and DCA⁻ ions and created the free volume for ion transport. As a result, this helpful mechanism resulted in S_i of 14.8 mV K⁻¹ and σ_i of 4.75×10^{-2} S cm⁻¹. Li and coworkers reported that vertically aligned channels containing negatively charged cellulosic were beneficial for facilitating the selective Na⁺ ion transport.⁸⁴ When poly(ethylene oxide)-NaOH i-TE electrolytes were introduced into oxidized delignified wood, S_i increased to 24 mV K⁻¹ due to the strengthened interaction between the negatively charged nanofibers and the Na⁺ ions in the i-TE electrolyte.

Second, water molecules in hydrogels evaporate naturally, which restricts their long-term stability. The incorporation of glycerol⁸⁵ or sorbitol⁸⁶ offered thermal tolerance in a wide temperature range and provided long-term stability to hydrogels at ambient conditions. P (AAm-AA) hydrogel was polymerized in a glycerol-water binary solution using UV initiation.⁸⁵ The glycerol in the P(AAm-AA) hydrogel formed hydrogen bonding with water molecules, thereby inhibiting the water evaporation at 60 °C temperature. Chen and coworkers reported calcium-alginate/PAAm organohydrogel with the solvent exchange method.⁸⁶ In contrast to a pure hydrogel, the prepared organohydrogels with glycerol, glycol, and sorbitol exhibited anti-freezing and -drying capability. These features were attributed to a decrease in "free water" molecules and the confinement of water molecules within the polymer networks. Overcoming such challenges of i-TE electrolytes is crucial for fulfilling sustainable energy harvesting needs and developing future wearable ITESCs.

C. Electrodes with high capacitance and stretchability

Equation (5) shows that electrodes with high capacitance play a significant role in increasing the E during the thermal charging of ITESCs. Au-TiO₂ NWs in a fully stretchable ITESC⁷¹ were employed owing to their inert stability and mechanical benefits; however, Au-TiO₂ NWs typically demonstrate lower capacitance compared to activated carbon, carbon nanotubes, and 2-dimensional nanosheets. These materials exhibit large surface areas and abundant pores, which provide numerous active sites for charge storage. This feature results in high capacitance values but intrinsically low stretchability, rendering it unsuitable for wearable applications. For the development of mechanically deformable electrodes for stretchable supercapacitors, researchers have explored various approaches.

The first approach was the fabrication of rigid electrodes (nanowires,⁸⁷ carbon nanotubes (CNTs),^{88,89} and graphene⁹⁰) on inherently stretchable materials, including polydimethylsiloxane^{87,90} and PU.^{88,89} Additionally, stretchable electrodes can be prepared by mixing elastic and active materials. For example, a gel electrolyte made of PVA, CNT, and PANI showed a specific capacitance of 284.6 mF cm⁻² and 75% stretchability.⁹¹ Chen *et al.* also demonstrated a stretchable hydrogel electrode incorporating gold NP and CNT into PAAm hydrogel.⁹²

The final approach involved the design of unique structures (e.g., waves, helices, textiles, reticulations, and serpentine patterns) that allow materials without stretchability to be stretched effectively.⁹³ Therefore, similar strategies for electrodes with high stretchability and capacitance can be explored for wearable ITESC applications.

D. Interfaces engineering between electrolytes/electrodes

Tough bonding for a stable interface between an i-TE electrolyte and electrodes is needed in practical wearable ITESCs because robust interfaces prevent delamination during the physical activities of human motion.⁹⁴ Wearable devices are routinely subjected to various mechanical stresses such as bending, stretching, and twisting. Additionally, during repetitive stretching/releasing cycles of a stretchable supercapacitor, mechanical stress affects its electrochemical performance.⁹⁵

For example, in previous studies, Au-TiO₂ NWs electrodes and i-TE electrolytes individually exhibited more than 250% stretchability prior to wearable device integration.⁷¹ However, when the vertically integrated ITESC was stretched to a high strain, only the elastic substrate/Au-TiO₂ NWs electrode underwent mechanical deformation, and the electrolytes did not interact with the mechanical strain because of slippage between the i-TE electrolyte/Au-TiO₂ NWs electrodes. To create a stable interface, poly(acrylic acid)^{95,96} and PVA⁹⁷ have been widely employed for adhesive interlayer or self-adhesive hydrogel sensors owing to their hydrophilic functional groups. Furthermore, Lee and coworkers reported that the positively charged amine groups in chitosan can enhance adhesion to human skin, which is beneficial for a wearable electrocardiogram sensor.⁹⁸ Another strategy to integrate hydrogel and various target substrates into a hybrid with a reliable interface was explored by covalently cross-linking hydrogel and substrates.^{99,100} These methods can be explored to improve the adhesive properties of i-TE electrolytes for future wearable ITESC.

VI. CONCLUSION

In summary, the development of thermodiffusion cells with stretchable i-TE electrolytes has been widely studied because of their large S_i . The state-of-the-art S_i of most stretchable i-TE electrolytes has surpassed 15 mV K⁻¹, which is approximately hundred times higher than that of conventional e-TE materials. A comprehensive overview of the recent advancements in stretchable i-TE electrolytes has been provided. Initially, this perspective focused on recent stretchable i-TE electrolytes composed of ternary polymer complexes, polymer:IL composites, and ion-conducting hydrogels. Subsequently, the challenges of recent ITESCs with the stretchable i-TE electrolytes were addressed and a fully stretchable ITESC was introduced for wearable applications. Finally, the future ITESCs are anticipated from the following perspectives: (1) device structure, (2) stable electrolytes with enhanced i-TE performance, (3) electrodes with high capacitance and stretchability, and (4) interface engineering between electrolytes/electrodes. As an emerging research area, there are challenges and opportunities for the application of wearable ITESCs.

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AUTHOR DECLARATIONS

Conflict of Interest

The author has no conflicts to disclose.

Author Contributions

Tae Hyun Park: Conceptualization (equal); Writing – original draft (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal).

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

NOMENCLATURE

Au-TiO ₂ NW	Au-coated titanium dioxide nanowire
<i>c</i>	concentration
ChCl	choline chloride
CNT	carbon nanotube
DES	eutectic solvent
DMAPS	[2-(methacryloyloxy)ethyl]dimethyl-(3-sulfo- propyl)ammonium hydroxide
DN	double network
e-TE	electronic thermoelectric
<i>E</i>	stored energy
EMIM ⁺ Cl ⁻	1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium chloride
EMIM ⁺ DCA ⁻	1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium dicyanamide
EMIM ⁺ OTf ⁻	1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium trifluoromethanesulfonate
EMIM ⁺ TFSI ⁻	1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium bis(trifluoromethyl- sulfonyl)imide
FS	fluoro-surfactant
i-TE	ionic thermoelectric
IL	ionic liquid
ITESC	ionic thermoelectric supercapacitor
<i>k</i>	thermal conductivity
Li ₂ SO ₄	lithium sulfate
Li ⁺ BF ₄ ⁻	lithium tetrafluoroborate
LiCl	lithium chloride
MACP	2-methacryloyloxyethyl phosphorylcholine
NaCl	sodium chloride
NaOH	sodium hydroxide
NP	nanoparticle
OITC	organic-inorganic ionic thermoelectric composites
PA	phytic acid
PAAm	poly(acrylamide)
PAAMPSA	poly(2-acrylamido-2-methyl-1-propanesulfonic acid)
PANI	polyaniline
P(AAm-AA)	poly(acrylamide-acrylic acid)
PEDOT	poly(3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene)
PEGDA	polyethylene glycol diacrylate
PU	polyurethane
PVA	polyvinyl alcohol
PVDF-HFP	poly(vinylidene fluoride-co-hexafluoropropylene)

Q^*	heat transport
R_s	sheet resistance
RH	relative humidity
SiO ₂	silicon dioxide
SO ₃ H	sulfonic acid
S_i	ionic Seebeck coefficient
S_T	Soret coefficient
TE	thermoelectric
V_{output}	output voltage
ZI	zwitterionic
ZIF-8	zeolitic imidazolate framework
ZT_i	ionic figure of merit
2-HEA	2-hydroxyethyl acrylate
σ_i	ionic conductivity
ΔT	temperature gradient

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